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Workpackage 2.3

Responsible Partner: NVI

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Author	Rebecca Davidson
Other contributors	Øivind Øines, Kristin Henriksen
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VALIDATION OF MAGNETIC CAPTURE REAL TIME PCR ASSAY

Scope

This deliverable describes the work carried out to establish the Magnetic capture Realtime PCR assay for *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the different laboratories in the project, verification of the method at each laboratory and a subsequent proficiency test sent to all partners.

Summary (of work carried out to date)

The methods (DNA extraction with automatic washing and manual washing protocols, as well as three realtime PCR protocols) and accompanying training video (for magnetic capture DNA extraction with manual washing) were published on Zenodo as project restricted technical notes in M41. If needed additional guidance, via digital meeting platforms, has been offered to the seven laboratories (BIOR, CVRL, INIAV, ISS, PIWET, SSI, VFL) that have registered for the training. So far, two laboratories have indicated they would like this. The verification and ring test protocol is being finalised and has now been shared with the nine laboratories (those participating in training plus FLI, RIVM) that have registered for participation in the ring test. Feedback from the participants will be included before the final protocol is published on Zenodo. The proficiency test will be carried out once the laboratories that are establishing the method have provided documentation to show that verification results were successful. The proficiency test will consist of 5 faecal samples per laboratory that have potentially been spiked with *E. multilocularis* eggs/worms. Participating laboratories should receive the proficiency test samples in month M47 as long as verification goes to plan and there are no further coronavirus-related restrictions to laboratory access

1. Introduction

MEME is an international multicentre collaborative project that aims to fill research gaps highlighted by international agencies for the detection and control of zoonotic parasites *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus* s.l. (Eg), causing alveolar echinococcosis (AE) and cystic echinococcosis (CE), respectively. MEME focuses on standardization, harmonization and validation of existing parasitological and molecular methods, and the development and comparative assessment of innovative molecular tools to detect Em and Eg in the food chain. Production of epidemiological data on the presence of Em/Eg eggs in the food chain focuses on vegetables for human consumption and on canine faeces in selected endemic countries. MEME provides a comprehensive set of integrative activities to harmonize procedures, improve the detection and produce epidemiological data on potential pathways of transmission of Em and Eg.

This deliverable focuses on the harmonization and validation of the Magnetic Capture real time PCR Assay for the detection of Em in fox faeces. There was a delay with the milestone in this task when the lead on the task was transferred from SVA (SVA withdrew from MEME in 2021) to NVI in M37.

The initial plan had been to develop SOPs for the magnetic capture methods: one with automatic washing steps (Swedish protocol) and one with manual washing steps (Norwegian protocol). After that we planned on providing training workshops in either Norway or Sweden depending on which protocol the participating laboratories planned to implement. Prior to SVA withdrawing from the project we were able to obtain their SOP for the automatic washing protocol but were not able to develop further teaching material for this method. The planned training workshops have been cancelled due to COVID-19, measures limiting personnel access to the laboratories and travel restrictions due to quarantine requirements. We developed teaching material (video) for the manual washing steps and are providing the laboratories with sample material to enable them to set up their own verification of the assay. Validation was then going to be conducted according to stage 3 and 4 of the OIE chapter on validation of diagnostic methods, since basic diagnostic characteristics of the test have already been published. Stage 3 validation means testing the assay in different laboratory settings, using equally aliquoted panels of more than 20 samples sent out to each laboratory as a proficiency test.

COVID-19 impacted our research work with our laboratories being restricted to clinical diagnostic work only during the series of closures that occurred in 2020 and 2021. We have for the moment scaled back our ambition for the number of samples in the proficiency test. Reference material has been collected from Arctic fox intestines in Svalbard (adult Em worms) and the faecal matrix is based upon homogenised red fox faeces from Norway that has previously tested negative for Em using the MC-realtime PCR assay.

So far, we have identified the laboratories interested in participating, the SOPs for the methods have been published on Zenodo and a SOP for the verification is in progress. Reference material has been collected but still needs to be prepared for shipping to the participating laboratories. This will be carried out in the next few weeks.

Once the method is set up and verified in the labs, the stage 3 proficiency test can be sent out. This is planned to take place M47-M48. Not until the data is analyzed, can partial stage 3 validation be considered completed. It is possible that participating laboratories may require troubleshooting assistance if the verification panel and/or the proficiency panel fail the test requirements. This would mean repeating verification and proficiency tests until the assay is performing satisfactorily at that laboratory. Therefore it is theoretically feasible that the validation will not be completed until mid 2022.

2. Identifying participating laboratories

All MemE partners were sent an email outlining the task and inviting them to participate. Participating laboratories have identified which methods they will be using as there a number of potential realtime PCR protocols that they can choose between. Many of the laboratories have already established these PCR methods and were therefore reluctant to change to a different protocol subsequent to DNA extraction. Some laboratories have requested to only participate in the proficiency test.

Table 1 Laboratories that have expressed an interest in participating in the MC-realtime PCR assay validation task in January 2021

Institute	Automatic washing SOP	Manual washing SOP	PCR Isakkson et al. 2014	PCR Øines et al. 2014	PCR Maas et al. 2016	Training magnetic capture	Training PCR
ISS			X			X	
FLI		X	X				
RIVM		X			X		
PIWET		X	X			X	X
SSI	?	?	X			X	X
INIAV		X	X			X	X
VFL		X	X			X	X
CVRL		X	X			X	X
BIOR	X	X	X	X		X	X

3. Developing the SOPs

SOPs have been developed and published on Zenodo as project restricted technical notes as follows:

1. SOP Magnetic capture of *Echinococcus multilocularis* from red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples: DNA extraction with automatic washing steps.
<https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.4746190.svg>
2. SOP Magnetic capture of *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA from red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples: DNA extraction with manual washing steps.
<https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.4897969.svg>

3. SOP 12S SsoFast Probe realtime PCR for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* eggs (based upon Isaksson et al. 2014). <https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.5499739.svg>
4. SOP EmrtCO1 realtime PCR for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* eggs (based upon Øines et al. 2014). <https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.4746181.svg>

One SOP that is still under development and to be finalised by 30th September 2021.

5. SOP Verification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* magnetic capture assay in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces and proficiency test

The third PCR protocol that some of the participants would like to use are:

Maas M, van Roon A, Dam-Deisz C, Opsteegh M, Massolo A, Deksné G, Teunis P, van der Giessen J. Evaluation by latent class analysis of a magnetic capture based DNA extraction followed by real-time qPCR as a new diagnostic method for detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in definitive hosts. *Vet Parasitol.* 2016 Oct 30;230:20-24. doi: 10.1016/j.vetpar.2016.10.016. Epub 2016 Oct 19. PubMed PMID: 27884437. This SOP has also been attached as an annex at the end of this deliverable.

4. Training materials

A training video was made showing each of the steps in the manual washing protocol. The film can be viewed here: <https://www.youtube.com/embed/hdo3mE8oMKE?rel=0>. If needed additional guidance can be provided and has been offered to the laboratories. Only two so far (ISS; SSI) have indicated that they would like additional training.

Currently no training has been established for the realtime PCR methods, nor has any been requested from the participating laboratories.

5. Verification procedure and initial proficiency test

An email was sent on 1st September 2021 to all the laboratories that expressed an interest in participating in this task to re-confirm their interest and to indicate if they are ready for verification, need further guidance, wish to participate in the proficiency test with another method or if they are no longer interested in participating in the task. The deadline for responses was set to 15th September 2021.

The verification SOP describes how each laboratory can verify that the assay is functioning within accepted parameters. If the verification assay does not perform as expected NVI can provide digital trouble-shooting guidance (via Teams or Skype) on a case by case basis. The material to be used in the verification steps has been collected and will be distributed to the participating laboratories once they have confirmed they are ready to proceed. The proficiency test samples will be sent at the same time and can be stored frozen until analysis can be carried out once the laboratory has successfully completed verification.

We hope to send out the verification and proficiency test material in mid-October with a 6 week deadline for the reporting of the results.

6. Results from the verification procedure

Lessons identified, pitfalls, lab performance.

7. Results from the initial proficiency test

To be inserted once the task will be accomplished.

8. Further validation work needed?

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ANNEX

SOP based on Maas et al. 2016

Magnetic capture based DNA extraction from fecal colon content

Day 1:

1. Weigh 1 gram faeces in a 15ml Greiner tube.
2. Suspend the faeces in 12ml lysis buffer [100 mM Tris HCl pH 8.0; 5 mM EDTA; 0,2% SDS; 200 mM NaCl]

max: 20 samples		
250 ml cell lysis buffer:		
1M Tris-HCl pH8		25 ml
0.5M EDTA pH8		2.5 ml
20% SDS		5 ml
5M NaCl		10 ml
Proteinase K	20x 50µl (>600 mAU/ml, solution)	1 ml
streptavidine	20x 50µl	1 ml
beads	20x 80µl	1,6 ml

3. Incubate for 10 min at 100°C.
4. Cool down to ambient temperature.
5. Centrifuge the sample for 10 s at 200×g.
6. Add 50µl proteinase K [Qiagen 20 mg/ml] per sample.
7. Incubate the sample for 2h at 56°C with regularly vortexing.
8. Incubate the sample for 10min at 100°C to inactivate the proteinase K.
9. Cool down to ambient temperature.
10. Centrifuge the sample for 15 min at 3500×g.
11. Bring 10ml supernatant in clean 15ml Greinertube.

Day 2:

Washing streptavidine sepharose

- Wash n x 50µl streptavidine sepharose (capaciteit: 300nmol biotine/ml) 3 times with 500µl-1000µl 1xPBS (centrifuge 20s short spin).
- Suspend the washed streptavidine sepharose in 1x PBS to the original volume

12. Add 50µl washed streptavidine sepharose to each sample.
13. Incubate 45 min, rotating at 10 rpm, at room temperature.
14. Centrifuge the sample for 15 min at 3500×g.
15. Bring 10 ml supernatant in clean 15ml Greinertube.

Capture

16. Add 10pmol capture oligo's to each sample [stock: 100µM. user stock: 1pmol oligo/µl].
17. Incubate 15 min at 95°C
18. Incubate 45 min at 60°C
19. Cool the samples, rotate at 10 rpm, at room temperature.

Washing dynabeads M270

- Suspend the beads (do not vortex)
- Take n x 80µl beads, pipette them in a 1.5ml tube.
- Place the tube in a magnet during 2 min.
- Discard the supernatant.
- Suspend the beads in n x 80µl 1X B&W buffer.
[2X B&W buffer: 10mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0), 1mM EDTA, 2.0M NaCl].

40ml B&W buffer 2X:

- 400µl 1M Tris-HCl (pH 8.0),
- 80µl 0.5M EDTA
- 16ml 5M NaCl
- 23.5 ml milliQ H₂O

- Place the tube in a magnet during 2 min.
- Discard the supernatant.
- Suspend the beads in n x 80µl 1X B&W buffer.

20. Add 2ml 5M NaCl to 10ml supernatant from step 19.
21. Then add 80µl washed beads to the 12ml sample.
22. Incubate the samples for 60 min, rotate 10 rpm, at room temperature.
23. Meanwhile put a heating block on 100°C.
24. Place the 15ml tube in a magnet and lay in on a shaking plate for 10 min (shake gently).
25. Discard the supernatant.
26. Suspend the beads (do not vortex) in 1ml 1x B&W buffer and pipette it in a 1.5ml tube.
27. Place the 1.5ml tube in a magnet.

